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CREATIVE INDUSTRIES IN RUSSIA IN POST COVID-19 TIME: THE CASE OF URALS REGION

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Abstract. The Middle Urals region is famous for its 300 years of industrial metallurgy history. The world-famous Russian metallurgy plants were built and worked here since 1702. During the XX century some of them were destroyed or replaced, but plants' buildings still exist. This rich industrial heritage nowadays has become a fundament for a uniqueness of Urals creative industries. Russian government and The Agency for Strategic Initiatives developed a program to renovate such territories. This all-Russian program is for the transformation of the territories of former industrial zones and abandoned buildings. The Middle Urals became a leader of the third stage of the federal project Creative Lab and a pilot region for creative industries. This article is devoted to the analyze of the regional development of creative industries and the usage of former industrial zone and abandoned buildings for it. There are several directions in which the work of the creative sector development is occurred in the Middle Urals: 1) writing the Strategy of the creative industries development; 2) development of a whole network of creative sites in the region on the territories of former plants and industrial facilities; 3) business education for creative entrepreneurs and new university educational standards for creatives industries.

Keywords: Middle Urals, creative industries, post-covid period, Creative Lab, business education for creative entrepreneurs

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КРЕАТИВНЫЕ ИНДУСТРИИ В РОССИИ В ПОСТ-КОВИДНЫЙ ПЕРИОД: НА ПРИМЕРЕ УРАЛЬСКОГО РЕГИОНА

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Аннотация. Уральский регион славится своей 300-летней историей промышленной металлургии. Известные на весь мир русские металлургические заводы были построены и работали здесь с 1702 года. В течение XX века некоторые из них были разрушены или заменены на современные, но заброшенные, полуразрушенные здания старинных демидовских заводов существуют до сих пор. Сегодня это богатое индустриальное наследие стало основой уникальности креативных индустрий Урала. Правительство Российской Федерации и Агентство стратегических инициатив разработали программу реновации заброшенных промышленных территорий, в том числе со старинными заводами. Это общероссийская программа преобразования территорий бывших промышленных зон и заброшенных зданий. Средний Урал стал лидером третьего этапа федерального проекта «Креативная лаборатория» и пилотным регионом для развития креативных индустрий в стране. Данная статья посвящена анализу развития регионального сектора креативных индустрий и использования для него бывших промышленных зон и заброшенных заводских зданий. В настоящее время выделяется несколько направлений, по которым ведется работа по развитию креативного сектора как в России, так и на Среднем Урале: 1) написание «Стратегии развития креативных индустрий»; 2) развитие сети креативных площадок региона на территориях бывших заводов и промышленных объектов; 3) бизнес-образование для творческих предпринимателей и новые университетские образовательные стандарты для креативных индустрий.

Ключевые слова: Средний Урал, креативные индустрии, пост-ковидный период, креативная лаборатория, бизнес-образование творческих предпринимателей

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Back in 2011, at the UN General Assembly, it was stated the need for a more visible and effective integration of culture into the development policies and strategies at all levels, in particular, in the post-2015 Sustainable Development Goals (SGDs)¹. Since that time the idea of controlled development of creative industries has been disseminated all over the world among all UN members. Governments started to work on development policies and find Agencies which would manage the process. [4, p.148-149].

In 2014 in Florence the UNESCO's Third World Forum on Culture and Cultural Industries (FOCUS) took place. As it was mentioned there «Valued at over \$620 billion, the global trade in cultural goods and services has doubled over the past decade, demonstrating that culture is a powerful force for both economic and social development. Cultural goods and services are not just ordinary merchandises that generate jobs, income, innovation and growth, they also contribute to social inclusion and justice»². It was very relevant for the world economy because of the trends that were examined by the World Economic Forum and mentioned in the Prof. Schwab's book³.

The world economy has experienced both a large number of rapid ups and several painful recessions over the past 75 years. But the rise that began in 2010 was lethargic. If until the early 1970s global growth peaked at 6% or more per year, and after, until 2008, it averaged at least 4%, then since then it has fallen to 3% or less... Global growth, which was only marginally faster than population growth, meant that a large proportion of the world's inhabitants actually experienced zero or negative economic growth. These economic conditions are demotivating to employees and companies themselves, as well as to the political establishment, as they point to slim chances for improvement⁴.

That is why creative sector got lots of attention, finance and administrative support on all levels from global to local ones in all regions and countries. [2].

It should be mentioned that the very idea about including culture into commoditization has been discussed since 1947 [8]. The role of culture like a society integration instrument and the role of creation like a differentiation one is still opened. [5, 8]. In our article we are talking about creative industries that are used like an alternative for rebuilding of destroyed heavy industry in our country.

In Russia they understand the importance of creative industries development and their role in national economy. [7]. The Agency for Strategic Initiatives became an operator of implementation on this global creative industries agenda. In 2018 it organized the so called Rurban project that was supported by ROSATOM⁵.

Rurban is a body that has programs of the Center for Urban Competence of the Agency for Strategic Initiatives to promote new projects (ASI). It was created in 2018 to develop and apply systematic approaches and models for replication aimed at building urban communities, involving citizens in solving development issues and improving the comfort level of the urban environment, as well as developing the urban economy. One of its projects is called Rurban Creative Lab. It is responsible for territorial transformation to creative clusters. Even before the governmental Concept was signed the Rurban Creative⁶ Lad initiated a competition based on the results of which regional teams for development of creative clusters were formed. Several regions of Russian Federation have been chosen for it, namely Irkutsk, Novgorod, Novosibirsk, Ryazan, Samara, Sverdlovsk, Tyumen, Udmurtia, Ulyanovsk and Khanty-Mansiysk regions.

«Within the framework of a cultural cluster, it is not necessary to create an expensive site, its basis is a project approach and activities that may take place on the territory of participating institutions, in the open air, sites of enterprises adapted for cultural events, other non-standard territories». [8, p. 81].

¹ World Culture Forum as an international dialogue platform. Diversity of Cultural Expressions. (2021, January 26). Retrieved May 30, 2022, from <https://en.unesco.org/creativity/policy-monitoring-platform/world-culture-forum-international>

² Third UNESCO World Forum on Culture and Cultural Industries - culture works for sustainable development. UNESCO. (2014, December 16). Retrieved May 30, 2022, from <https://en.unesco.org/news/third-unesco-world-forum-culture-and-cultural-industries-culture-works-sustainable-developmen-0>

³ Schwab, K., & Vanham, P. (2021). Stakeholder capitalism a global economy that works for progress, people and planet. Wiley. – pp. 40-79.

⁴ Schwab, K., & Vanham, P. (2021). Stakeholder capitalism a global economy that works for progress, people and planet. Wiley. – pp. 44-45.

⁵ Rurban.space. (n.d.). Retrieved June 10, 2022, from <https://rurban.space/main>

⁶ The Concept #2613-p devoted to the development of the Creative Industries and Mechanisms for the Implementation of Their State Support in Large and Largest Urban Agglomerations Until 2030. (n.d.). Retrieved June 1, 2022, from <http://static.government.ru/media/files/HEXNAom6EJunVlxBCjIAAtAya8FAVDUfP.pdf>

Why has Sverdlovsk region been included in this program?

The Middle Urals region is famous for its 300 years of industrial metallurgy history. The first metallurgy plant was built here in 1630 and the world-famous Russian metallurgy plants were built and worked here since 1702 when Peter the Great initiated industrial development of Russia. During the XX century some of them were destroyed or replaced, but plants' buildings still exist. This rich industrial heritage nowadays has become a fundament for a uniqueness of Urals creative industries. Russian government and The Agency for Strategic Initiatives developed a program to renovate such territories. This Russian program is for the transformation of the territories of former industrial zones and abandoned buildings. Sverdlovsk region is a pilot one for creative industries in Russia.

Back in 2019, before the Concept⁷ and competition⁸ were excepted one of Demidov's abandoned plant in Sysert became a place for the non-commercial private initiative «Letonazavode» (Summer at the Plant). This project demonstrated the creative potential of such zones, and its author even met with President Putin to present this project. The meeting emphasized extreme importance and significance of the chosen way.

The Sverdlovsk Regional Business Support Fund is a practical oriented supervisor of the creative cluster development in Sverdlovsk region. It approached the task very responsibly. On February 28, 2021 it initiated the Creative Industries Development Strategic Session in Sverdlovsk region. The professional facilitation company Energy of Ideas moderated it.

The main idea of the session was to create a common information field, to get answers to questions, to form a team of initiators of creating a production center and to plan the first steps for the creative industries development in Sverdlovsk region. The expected results included a list of ranked relevant questions on the topic using which the regional government could create a production center; all participants clearly understand the purpose of creation and the essence of

the work of the production center in order to participate in the work of the center or not; interested persons can join the team of 18 initiators; the first steps that are necessary for project implementation are outlined; participants understand what is next step, what to prepare for; and feel like a part of the project team.

Minister of Investment and development of the Sverdlovsk region opened the session.

The participants developed ideas for the cluster, its risks and steps that should be made to achieve the goals. They composed a list of the clusters' users, risks and steps to overcome risks and attract target users. Much of attention was given to the description of the clusters' teams and supporting of motivation of them. Special impact was made on the planned results and the future image of creative cluster. On the other hand, the question of finance was considered.

The second meeting organized by the Sverdlovsk Regional Business Support Fund was devoted to the discussion of the draft law "On the Creative Industries of the Sverdlovsk Region" and taken place on May 28, 2021. The aim of the meeting was to present the participants the law, then answer their questions and after that to have a session of developing and collecting their recommendations for the draft. The participants would like the government answers such very important questions as what creative product is, whether «free artists» are subjects of the creative industries in case they are not registered as legal entities, what the authorized executive body is responsible for the creative industries, etc. In total, 6 pages of changes to the thesaurus of the law were proposed by the professional community.

The second topic was the completeness of the provided measures of support. And again, professionals of the creative sector asked very productive questions. They would like to know whether the body which specifically provides consulting support, if some support mechanism is implemented, if there will be different degrees of support depending on the level of development of creative entities, etc. As a result of the session all 20 pages of suggestions were taken into account and made into law⁹.

⁷ The Concept #2613-p devoted to the development of the Creative Industries and Mechanisms for the Implementation of Their State Support in Large and Largest Urban Agglomerations Until 2030. (n.d.). Retrieved June 1, 2022, from <http://static.government.ru/media/files/HEXNAom6EJunVixBCjIAtAya8FAVDUfP.pdf>

⁸ Rurban.space. (n.d.). Retrieved June 10, 2022, from <https://rurban.space/main>

⁹ The author of this article thanks the Energy of Idea company for the providing the reports of these two sessions that were used here.

These activities demonstrate, from the one hand, the high level of professionalism of creative clusters participants, their openness and desire to work, to create and to develop the region, and, on the other hand, the readiness of the local and federal government to listen and implement ideas of the professionals of the sector.

On September 20, 2021 the Russian Government approved the Concept #2613-p which is devoted to the development of the Creative Industries and Mechanisms for the Implementation of the State Support Measures in Large and Largest Urban Agglomerations till 2030¹⁰. This Concept was developed in accordance with the Decree of the President of the Russian Federation dated December 24, 2014 No. 808 «On Approval of the Fundamentals State Cultural Policy and The Spatial Development Strategy of the Russian Federation for the Period up to 2025», approved by the Decree of the Government of the Russian Federation dated February 13, 2019 No. 207-r. The main goals of the Concept of the development of Creative Industries are to give Russian people the opportunity for self-realization and development of their talents, to provide the decent, efficient work and successful entrepreneurship, and facilitate the digital transformation.

The pandemic period demonstrated that creative and intellectual input into the product had been playing a significant role in economy and might use digital technologies for it. These technologies open the wide opportunities for the dissemination of the entrepreneurial results all over the world crossing borders in a new global transformed world.

Structural changes caused by Covid-19 pandemic and concomitant economical, technological and social processes made the approval of this Concept timely. The job cuts, from the one hand, and entering the economical arena such categories of employees like women, young people, disabled persons, on the other hand, demand the alternative ways of employ-

ments, and not automated creative industries are excellent directions to overcome pandemic and changes mentioned above.

The creative industries sector has the potential to create high added value that makes it attractive both for entrepreneurs and investors. Many areas of the sector are characterized by a relatively low barrier to entry into the market, that makes it possible for general public like women, disabled people etc. to develop their business, allows them to overcome the limitations of development, related to the insufficient volume of the local market and the remoteness of the entrepreneur's place of residence, to preserve human capital in the regions and municipalities, to ensure balanced territorial development.

These characteristics of creative industries allow to describe them like a humanitarian sector of economy. One example that illustrated that fact can be found in a book *A global Economy That Works for Progress, People and Planet* written by Klaus Schwab and Peter Vanham:

Puty Puart was thinking about her own future. She had been friends with Annisa (a Bandung mushroom entrepreneur) since college, where she studied engineering geology and later worked as a geologist in Borneo for the French international energy company Total. Life was not easy for her. Puty's husband worked in Jakarta and they only saw each other once every two weeks on weekends. Then Puty became pregnant and made an important decision for herself - to quit her job, move to her husband in Jakarta and become a housewife mom. After turning down a job as a geologist, she planned to try herself as an illustrator and graphic designer. Puty could no longer do the same things as in Total, but she got a chance to devote time to her creative hobby, sitting at home with a child.

The choice made allowed Puty to achieve much more, than she expected. Her blogs and illustrations about the life of a young mother quickly attracted the attention of mothers of her age in Indonesia to the content she created, and thanks to Instagram, she was

¹⁰ The Concept #2613-p devoted to the development of the Creative Industries and Mechanisms for the Implementation of Their State Support in Large and Largest Urban Agglomerations Until 2030. (n.d.). Retrieved June 1, 2022, from <http://static.government.ru/media/files/HEXNAom6EJunVlxBCjIAtAya8FAVDUfP.pdf>

known far beyond her native country. One of the projects even helped Puty travel to New York. In the competition of one-minute videos, which was held by the organizing committee of the international award "Emmy", she became the winner. This event marked the beginning of her international career as a freelance artist. While working from home, she received an invitation from Facebook's art director in San Francisco to participate in the company's project. It was necessary to create "stickers" for social networks, adapted to the needs of their many users in Indonesia. On another project, Puty designed personalized greeting cards for a woman in the United Arab Emirates. Puty never met her client in real life, but online negotiations were ongoing, and the client paid for the work performed on the project through PayPal within the agreed time frame. Sometime later, a Singapore-based company approached Puty to create illustrations for their clothing brand. Refusing to work at Total, Puty gained a huge amount of social media following in return, and this popularity brought clients from Indonesia and other countries to her¹¹.

This excerpt demonstrated the very peculiarities on creative industries, we see that practically everyone who has a creative potential can start their one business.

How it is mentioned in the Concept devoted to the development of the Creative Industries and Mechanisms for the Implementation of the State Support Measures in Large and Largest Urban Agglomerations Until 2030: «the sector of creative industries provides a significant contribution to the global economy namely the average share of the creative industries sector in world GDP is 6.6 percent, in developed countries this share reaches 8-12 percent with an average annual growth of 15 percent, which significantly exceeds average growth rates of the global economy (this trend is projected to continue in the medium term)». But in Russia the potential of the creative economy sector is not enough implemented. The share of creative industries in the economy of our country is only 2.23 percent.

Creative industries are important accelerator for the special development of Russian Federation as a

whole and Sverdlovsk region in particular. According to the Spatial Development Strategy of the Russian Federation for the period up to 2025 one of the main problems of spatial development of the Russian Federation is insufficient number of economic growth centers to ensure the acceleration of the economic growth of the Russian Federation.

The main problems of the spatial development of the Russian Federation also include a low level of entrepreneurial activity in most small and medium-sized towns in rural areas, territories outside the largest urban agglomerations. Taking into account these trends while implementing the Spatial Development Strategy of the Russian Federation for the period up to 2025 it is necessary to focus and select as support priorities the types of entrepreneurs based on the use of the results of creative, intellectual activity, regardless of specific types of economic activity, sectors of the economy and (or) share of material (production) component in the final product and service. The government realized that the priorities of the activities of public authorities of all levels should be an increase in the share of such entrepreneurship in all sectors of the economy. Special attention should be paid to promising economic specializations of the constituent entities of the Russian Federation, as well as the gradual inclusion of creative industries among such specializations. The development of creative industries, both in terms of value and volume, entails a multiplier economic effect.

The support of creative industries must lead to increasing of the tax base; increasing a number of new workplaces on local and state levels; reducing disproportions in socio-economic development; and increasing the tourist attractiveness of the territories.

The Russian government instructed regional branches of the Business and Entrepreneurship Support Fund to do its best in implementing these ideas. On December 20, 2021 the Governor of Sverdlovsk region, The Mayor of Yekaterinburg and the Head of Sverdlovsk Regional Business and Entrepreneurship Support Fund signed an agreement that legally launched a project to create a network creative cluster on the territory of the Sverdlovsk region with a central site on Weiner Street, 16 in Yekaterinburg.

¹¹ Schwab, K., & Vanham, P. (2021). Stakeholder capitalism a global economy that works for progress, people and planet. Wiley. – pp.127 – 128.

As mentioned above, the Sverdlovsk Region participates in the federal program for the transformation of unused territories and abandoned industrial zones into creative clusters «Urban Creative Lab» of the Agency for Strategic Initiatives. Its main task is to enliven spaces into places of attraction for representatives of the creative entrepreneurial community, residents of the region and tourists.

To date, there are several creative clusters in the Sverdlovsk region. Let's consider each of them separately.

The territories in Chernostochinsk, Nizhny Tagil and Sysert were the first to be «activated» on the territory of the Sverdlovsk region.

Art Residence in Chernostochinsk.

On the territory of an old metallurgy Demidov's plant in the village of Chernostochinsk near Nizhny Tagil, a project is being implemented to make a creative space «Art Residence». Its authors are «The My Business Center» in Nizhny Tagil (created by the Sverdlovsk Regional Business and Entrepreneurship Support Fund. Sergy Fedoreev is the Head of it) and local entrepreneur Alexander Bykov, who bought the building in 2013 and occupied a small part of it with a furniture workshop.

Fig.1 The Chernostochinsk plant view

After several cultural events that took place in our center, it became clear to me that creative people had great commercial potential, but it has not been realized. Along with the idea of creating a platform for the sale of works of art, last year we came up with the

¹² The first international art residence for artists in Nizhny Tagil may appear on the squares of the old Chernostochinsky plant. Nizhny Tagil's and Sverdlovsk Region News - Media Agency "Mezhdu

idea of making a creative accelerator, where we would give creative people entrepreneurial competence," says Sergey Fedoreev¹².

The creative cluster in Chernostochinsk is a space placed on the territory of the former metallurgy plant founded by Akinfiy Demidov in 1726, in the village of Chernostochinsk, which houses the new museum of platbands "Fancy Balusters". It is an authentic place near the dam of the Chernostochinsky pond. Now it is an unusual and stylish creative space with workshops, an exhibition hall, concert venues, a pottery workshop, its own puppet theater and a souvenir shop.

Fig. 2 ArtResidence in Chernostochinsk

Fig. 3 Souvenirs, Chernostochinsk

The Art Residence project was included in the number of projects participating in the 100 City Leaders 2020 program of the Agency for Strategic Initiatives. The Chernostochinsk's idea entered the top

Strook". (2020, October 22). Retrieved June 10, 2022, from <https://mstrok.ru/news/naploshchadyah-starogo-chnostochinskogo-zavoda-mozhet-poyavitsya-pervaya-v-nizhnem-tagile>

twenty. In total, 604 applications from more than 200 settlements of the country were received for the competition. For these several years of its works the Art Residence has developed a lot of activities, its program is oriented to the promoting of the specificity of the local territory namely workshops from local artists; lectures from art experts and historians, who tell about Demidov, his plants and many other things about this village; celebrates some traditional Slavic and orthodox holidays. The target audiences of the Residence are schoolchildren from Nizhny Tagil and Yekaterinburg, weekend travelers and tourists. One of the problems of this residence and the future task is how to involve the local people into the activities of the Residence. Its representative Elena Kirilyuk is responsible for the development the project.

Creative Factory in Sysert

Another finalist of the federal competition 100 City Leaders 2020 from the Sverdlovsk region was the Creative Factory project in Sysert. This creative cluster is based on the Turchaninov-Solomirsky metallurgy plant. It was initiated in 2019 as it was mentioned above.

Fig. 4 The Turchaninov-Solomirsky Ironworks, Sysert

The first buildings of the Turchaninov-Solomirsky plant in Sysert were built in 1732 after iron ore was found here at the end of the 17th century. Until the middle of the 19th century, the enterprise was considered one of the most advanced in the world, but without refurbishment, the plant became very outdated. The Ural industrialists here tried to use cheap labor and did not want to master new methods and technologies. In Soviet times, engines for the famous Malyutka washing machines were made here, and with the collapse of the USSR, the plant finally fell into decay.

For the last 30 years, the buildings of the Turchaninov-Solomirsky metallurgy plant in Sysert have been empty, gradually turning into ruins. But in 2018, the entrepreneur Yan Kozhan established an NGO Sysert Development Agency and gradually initiated several cultural projects: «Letonazavode» («The Summer at the Plant»), «Ural Creative Camp», «Purely So!», and «Touristic cluster». And in 2020 «The Summer at the Plant» project gave the metallurgy plant a second life. During the first season, more than 20,000 people visited the place, and in November 2020, Vladimir Putin paid attention to it. The President of Russia liked the initiative, and Sysert's experience became the starting point for testing this practice in other regions of Russia.

The peculiarity of this place is that it is a season place that works only in summer because the plant premises has not been reconstructed yet and they can't work in winter although the Sysert Development Agency invited an architect Narine Tyutcheva who developed the reconstruction concept, nonetheless this process is bringing slowly into existence.

In spite of all difficulties this initiative is in demand with Yekaterinburg and Sysert citizens and tourists, thanks to the governmental support and organizer's energy and resources. It has a wide advertisement that helped to attract more than 20 000 people in 2020 to it.

To attract as many people as they can the organizers cooperate with famous creative teams and celebrities of federal level. For instance, they provided a platform for the famous in The European Union and very popular in Yekaterinburg «Nikolay Kolyada Theater», ballet team Province Dances etc. All activities are free of charge for the visitors.

This year the project has found money to make some part of the plant all-season working. The whole budget for the reconstruction is 1 billion rubles.

Creative cluster Samorodok (Prill) in Nizhny Tagil

At the end of 2021, as part of the development of creative clusters in the Sverdlovsk Region, the regional government decided to establish a site in Nizhny Tagil. It is base in the very downtown in the building of former college Samorodok that gave the name to the whole cluster.

«We chose «Samorodok». The most important factor was the location - the city center. I hope the

walls will help us, because a handcraft college was located in the building. Our task is to carry out high-quality training of teams, to create centers for them to be managed by professionals. We plan to upgrade the event agenda related to the development of creative industries: these are various forums, meetings, festivals», explained Victoria Kazakova, Minister of Investment and Development of the Sverdlovsk Region.

The head of the project and the director of the NGO «Creative industries and technologies» Ekaterina Tretyakova created a really interesting place with very rich program. For instance, the day before the International Women's Day on March 8 they organize a one-day fair Garage. The organizers invite self-employed people and entrepreneurs to participate in the fair. The craftsmen who create ceramics, jewelry, clothes and accessories, designers, second-hand shops, vintage online shops, artists, hand makers and customizers also are invited to participate. The garage sale is a unique opportunity to sell goods of own production, join the concept of smart consumption, which is popular all over the world, give new life to old things, have a good time and buy original gifts for the holiday. Lots of art and photo exhibitions were organized here.

The main idea of this cluster is to join creative entrepreneurs of Nizhny Tagil under the auspices of Samorodok.

Fig. 5 The plant premises inside

The former Aramil cloth factory, known as Zlokazovskaya, is included into the network of creative spaces. In 2021, the project won a grant. The Presidential Fund for the Cultural Initiatives Support gave them 2 545 851 Rub. to create the Overcoat Museum and the project «Sun in Threads: Creative space for Ural Artisans».

Fig. 6 Samorodok Nizhny Tagil creative cluster Fashion Factory PRO-Textile in Aramil

Fig. 7 Zlokazovskaya Cloth factory in Aramil

The history of the development of the cloth factory is an important part of the history of the small town. The factory was the best enterprise in pre-revolutionary Russia for the production of textiles; during the Second World War, overcoat cloth was produced here, every fourth overcoat for the Red Army was sewn here. In the post-war period, until the beginning of the 21st century, the factory was one of the largest enterprises in the textile industry of Russia. Of course, for the Aramil citizens and the nearest settlements, the factory is the personification of their history and identity. The projects implemented on this site are united by the historical component of the territory. The Overcoat Museum and the Art Gallery are opened here providing a platform for exhibitions, fairs, fashion shows, festivals, concerts, etc.

The implementation of the idea to turn the building of the former enterprise into a venue for a regular regional festival of textile artisans does not only draw

attention to the historical and cultural context. It also joins the efforts of young designers who come up with bright holiday installations and design creative spaces. Artisans who create author's collections of clothes work here too. This cluster provides a place for discussions, meetings, integration of the creative potential of masters of young and mature age.

Two next clusters are located in Yekaterinburg, a Sverdlovsk region capital.

Makletsky House cluster in Yekaterinburg

This cluster has a principal difference from the previous ones. It is organized and closely linked with the municipal Yekaterinburg History Museum. The director of the museum was the initiator and ideologist of the project, and it is based in one of the museum's buildings.

The House of Makletsky Center for Urban Practices (this is a full name of the project) is a new format of a creative cluster that brings together urban researchers, representatives of the creative industries and activists working with the themes of the city, historical and cultural heritage. The purpose of the cluster is to create an infrastructure for the cooperation and implementation of joint projects of organizations, communities, citizens interested in the study, presentation and development of Yekaterinburg.

Fig. 8 The House of Makletsky Center for Urban Practices, Yekaterinburg

On the basis of the cluster, there is a resource center for residents, a family history center, a coworking space for city initiatives, art residences, a Ural design market, and a podcast space. The cluster is a launching pad for the implementation of projects for creative and socially active citizens.

This is a joint project of the Yekaterinburg History Museum and the City Initiatives Fund with the support of the Department of Culture of Yekaterinburg.

To implement the project, they chose the Makletsky House at the cross-road of Turgenev and Pervomaiskaya streets. The monument of architectural heritage used to be the estate of Ilya Makletsky, pre-revolutionary director of the Siberian Trade Bank, public figure and philanthropist. In Soviet times, the House of People's Judges was located here, later - the Regional Institute for the Protection of Children's and Adolescents' Health, and finally a children's clinic. The main historical two-story house was added on two floors in 1934.

Today the building has four floors each of which has its own topic and goal. The opening of the first floor, Living Room, took place on April 6, 2019 as a part of the fourth History Fest. Here you can learn about the projects of the Makletsky House, drink coffee, listen to lectures and buy local souvenirs. There is also an open library with publications and books about Yekaterinburg and the Sverdlovsk region.

The second floor is a Research Center. The floor is beautiful with a 19th century fireplace and arched windows overlooking the city. Here you can work with an open historical base, and the specialists of the center will help you to research the history of the city and your family.

The third floor is a Space of Creative Industries. Studios of musicians and photographers will appear here. Workshops and showrooms of local artists, clothing and decor designers will be located next to them.

The fourth floor is a Residence of City Initiatives. The last floor of the house is being transformed into an open co-working space for employees of cultural, social and other developing city projects.

Part of the center will operate in the format of a residence. People can get a room in the Makletsky House for a period of 6 to 24 months. In addition, it will be possible to hold your own events there.

«Domna» creative cluster in Yekaterinburg

This cluster was initiated in 2021 and had opened its doors in 2022. It houses the front offices of creative structures, a regional production media center, and a showroom of creative products. The city

mayor gave 2500 square meters building in pedestrian historical street of Yekaterinburg for this project. This space is planned to house a shop of local artisans, a collective use center for clothing production, digital fitting rooms, youth IT coworking, webinar and podcast studios. In addition, the cluster on Weiner Street, 16 will become a platform for city, regional and federal events.

Fig. 9 Domna, Yekaterinburg

«Domna» occupied the second floor of the building. The reconstruction of the building costed more than 150 million rubles. The project in Yekaterinburg is supervised by the Sverdlovsk regional government, City Administration, and the Sverdlovsk Regional Business and Entrepreneurs Support Fund.

It is assumed that the described above sites created in the Sverdlovsk region will be conditionally united into one network, the central link of which will be a creative cluster in Yekaterinburg on Weiner Street, 16.

Along with the mentioned creative sites all over the Sverdlovsk region there are some other ones namely Uralmash in Yekaterinburg – a cluster for rock musicians and Atom in Novouralsk. Of course, not everything is as easy as it might seem. Entrepreneurs have to overcome a number of serious difficulties in the way of implementing their ideas. For instance, the creative cluster project at Uralmash stalled even before its implementation began because the building is a federal property.

Five buildings of a famous Soviet plant Uralmach are planned to be given as a cluster: the plant management of the Ural Heavy Machine Building Plant, the entrance of the enterprise, the former laboratory of the Plant, the former hotel "Madrid" and a res-

idential building. All of them are architectural monuments and some of them are in disrepair. Now almost all areas, with the exception of some rooms, are not used in any way. A large investor has not been found yet, and the owner of the buildings, a federal agency, agrees to provide the buildings only for rent, at a rate that is called too high in the cluster. Parties continue to negotiate the question, but the answer and decision has not achieved yet.

The importance of the renovation of old factories heritage and the creative clusters development in the region is emphasized by the fact that new sector has got not only financial but administrative support.

The ideologist of the project for the development of creative industries in the region is the Ministry of Investment and Development of the Sverdlovsk Region, the operator is the Sverdlovsk Regional Business and Entrepreneurs Support Fund. With the assistance of the Fund, the sites are filled with resident entrepreneurs.

The main industrial fair of Russia Innoprom that is held in Yekaterinburg is involved as the main open stage for the meeting and discussion of the development plans of the sector. Last, 2021 year on the booth of Sverdlovsk region they openly discussed the problems with the Uralmash cluster mentioned above. This year the whole day was devoted to the creative industries. The organizers called it Creative Thursday. The panel «Creative Thursday. Experience in the Development of Creative Entrepreneurship in the Urals» was devoted to several questions: network creative cluster of the Sverdlovsk region: sites and their residents; the emergence of new creative clusters in the cities and towns of the Sverdlovsk region; creative cluster as a source of changes in the urban environment; the impact of creative entrepreneurship on the service of domestic and inbound tourism. All heads of the described clusters participated in this panel and shared their experience and results of the year of working.

Along with the development of destroyed plants the creative clusters in Urals contribute the development of female entrepreneurship in the region. 50% of the mentioned creative clusters' Heads are women. There are some researches devoted to this issue. [6]. According to them women might be very successful in

the sphere of creative industries and might facilitate their development in our country.

The author of this article is one of the creative cluster head too. She is a CEO of the Agency for Cultural and Science diplomacy and focuses the activities on cultural and science projects devoted to creative industries and cultural policies of BRICS alliance. In 2021 the Agency for Cultural diplomacy won the President grant for the online project Meet BRICS Art that was devoted to the online exhibition of the BRICS professional artists and the 10 online-meetings of them. The main idea was to get the world acquainted with the professional artists from alliance and to form a community of professional artists of BRICS. The project demonstrated huge importance of cooperation among BRICS creative entrepreneurs. Another direction of the Agency is a School for Cultural Diplomacy for the creative entrepreneurs from BRICS. Now the Agency plans to develop the idea of including the Yekaterinburg city into the BRICS Creative cities UNESCO. There are some other projects that the Agency plans to realize next year.

Conclusion

All the considered clusters demonstrate high potential for the future development of the territories. In spite of the same market all of them have their own specificity and use local cultural and historical peculiarities. In fact, it is one of the features of creative industries. This our observation is confirmed by some other researchers. For instance, the same process we see in the Sakha Republic (Yakutia) [10] and Kazakhstan [4, p. 151-152]. So, it means that the creative industries development will help to actualize local cultural identities and histories that is extremely important for understanding of cultural richness of Russia and the development of local people. [3].

In spite of the facts demonstrated above it is an experiment where the federal government tested the mechanisms of development and support the humanitarian sector of economy. As some researchers mentioned our country is searching its model of creative economy. [9].

Today they singled out some difficulties that represent tasks that should be solved in the future. Here are some of them.

The concept of creative industries directly associated with regional and national specifics, differs from country to country, there is no universal applied understanding of creative industries in the world. As a result, simple obvious and cross-cutting criteria for all sectors of the economy recognition of companies that belong to the creative sector economy, are absent. Measures of state support (small and medium-sized businesses, industry, export) are formed for priority industries, industrial economy and do not take into account the specifics of the creative industry development. In particular, at all levels of government, it is stimulated acquisition of fixed assets and equipment (subsidized interest rates, etc.), but wages are not subsidized, which forms the basis of the costs of the creative economy sector.

Creation innovation support ecosystems, despite of their similarity, is oriented exclusively for technological projects (IT sector, medicine, pharmaceuticals, energy cluster, etc.). In spite of the fact that this sector is paid for out of federal, regional and municipal programs, they are fragmented and uncoordinated. The institutional nature of financial instruments leads to the fact that most promising companies that create products at the intersection of culture, digital technology, and industry, are out state focus.

Tax legislation of the Russian Federation and the system tax administration does not fully take into account the specifics of creative entrepreneurship. For example, the circulation of intellectual rights at the stage of creating a product and (or) service does not create an added value and the monetization of the results of creative work usually occurs at the time of consumption of the final product. Moreover, there are no special mechanisms encouragement of authors to create.

Creative industries collide with the inability to unambiguously determine the optimal mode taxation of created products and services. The risks of re-qualification of transactions, administrative fines and other sanctions increase for entrepreneurs.

The creative industries are critically dependent on the security and efficiency of managing intellectual property. However, the existing modes of circulation of intellectual rights, state registration of transactions with such rights and mechanisms for their protection do not allow to multiply number of results to be turnover.

Russian federal government formed several ways of developing the humanitarian sector of economy. State support for the development of creative industries and creative entrepreneurship carried out in the following areas:

- creation of territorial infrastructure for creative entrepreneurship of both general purposes including social, and special (professional) infrastructure focused on specific types of creative and (or) entrepreneurial activity;
- development of a system of knowledge and competencies, both creative and entrepreneurial nature, including inviting specialists from both Russia and abroad to transfer non-formalized knowledge and skills;
- formation of an information support system, including, among other things, the possibility of commercial and non-commercial use of elements of historical and cultural, intangible heritage;
- formation of a financial infrastructure focused on various stages of maturity of creative entrepreneurship, including the "seed stage" (small grants), the stage of ensuring sustainability of venture and the scaling stage (entering new markets);

- elaboration of proposals to clarify the mechanisms of taxation, including jointly with the subjects of the Russian Federation, for regional and local taxes and tax administration, taking into account the specifics of creative entrepreneurship in terms of making, distributing products with a high share of creative work, developing a specialized infrastructure;
- development of a service support system for the legal protection of transactions with intellectual property rights and protection of the intellectual activity rights in online and offline environments, other necessary legal and financial services;
- creation of ecosystems attractive for the concentration of talents, the implementation of ambitious public and state projects that require active communication and interaction of various people, territories, institutions;
- development of export infrastructure - service support expansion of goods and services, promotion of the export of intellectual property rights to global markets.

Such a complex attention and efforts aimed at the development of the creative sector will be fruitful in the nearest future.

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